

Systematic Mapping Study on Change Tracking in MDSE: Approaches and Tools

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Abstract—Each year, numerous papers related to change tracking in Model-Driven Software Engineering (MDSE) are published, making it difficult to follow the evolution and trends of the available artifacts. The main objective of this study is to provide an overview of the approaches and tools used for change tracking in MDSE. To this end, a systematic mapping study was conducted in which 2565 distinct papers were screened. Ultimately, 37 primary studies were selected to be analyzed quantitatively and qualitatively. As a result, we classified the approaches/paradigms and identified 17 distinct tools supporting this activity. The evidence suggests that while the field remains active, the research focus is shifting from low-level differencing to semantic-aware strategies, though challenges regarding scalability and interoperability remain open.

Index Terms—Model evolution, Change traceability, Model differencing, Model versioning

I. INTRODUCTION

Model-Driven Software Engineering (MDSE) has emerged as a prominent paradigm in software development, promoting the use of models as first-class artifacts throughout the software lifecycle [1]. By leveraging higher levels of abstraction, MDSE aims to increase productivity, improve software quality, and manage the complexity of modern systems [2]. In this paradigm, models are not mere documentation but are central to analysis, design, and even code generation through automated transformations [3]. However, like any software artifact, models are not static. They are subject to continuous evolution driven by changing requirements, bug fixes, and design improvements.

The inevitability of change is a fundamental principle in software engineering [4]. In traditional, code-centric development, mechanisms for change tracking, versioning, and collaboration, such as Git¹, are standard practice. These tools are essential for coordinating teamwork, maintaining a historical record of modifications, and enabling operations like branching and merging [5].

When development shifts to a model-driven approach, the need for change tracking mechanisms remains essential. The complex, often graphical and structurally

intricate nature of models poses unique challenges that traditional text-based version control systems are ill-equipped to handle. Tracking the evolution of models is necessary for understanding design rationale, ensuring consistency across different artifacts, supporting collaborative modeling, and performing essential operations like model comparison (diff) and merging [6].

While substantial research has been dedicated to this problem, the resulting approaches and tools are spread across an array of publications. This dispersion has led to a fragmented and sometimes overwhelming landscape for both new researchers entering the field and practitioners seeking effective solutions. A systematic mapping study is therefore necessary to cut through this complexity, providing a structured panorama of the state-of-the-art, identifying what has already been achieved, and clarifying which challenges remain open.

This paper aims to provide this structured panorama. The primary goal is to identify, classify, and analyze the existing body of research on change tracking in MDSE. Specifically, we aim to: **(1)** Identify and classify the approaches proposed for change and evolution tracking in MDSE contexts. **(2)** Map the existing tools and frameworks that implement or support such change tracking mechanisms. **(3)** Analyze the current body of research to highlight trends and research gaps in the literature.

To achieve these goals, we conducted a systematic mapping study (SMS) to provide an overview of the field of change tracking in MDSE. An SMS is a form of secondary study, performed to aggregate and categorize the available evidence from primary studies on a specific topic [7]. Therefore, it provides an overview of a research area, identifying the quantity and type of the available research, and helps to highlight its trends and gaps.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II explains the planning of the systematic mapping. Section III presents the conduction of the study. Section IV discusses the findings. Section V describes the threats to the validity of the work. Finally, Section VII concludes the paper and outlines future works.

¹<https://git-scm.com/>

II. PLANNING

To achieve the expected outcome from this SMS, it is fundamental to follow a well-defined process that includes searching, screening, assessing, and analyzing the studies. In the SMS, we follow the process proposed by Petersen et al. [7], which describes a standard for conducting SMSs in Software Engineering. Hence, the process is divided into three main phases: Planning, Conduction, and Reporting. The Planning phase is described within this section. The Conduction of the study is presented in Section III, while the Reporting of the findings is detailed and discussed in Section IV.

A. Scope and objective

In this work the main objective is provide a comprehensive overview of how change tracking is addressed within the MDSE domain. We focused on identifying and classifying the main approaches, mechanisms, and tools proposed to support model evolution, traceability, and comparison. Furthermore, we aimed to map the technical characteristics of these solutions to understand the current state of the art. This study is intended to help researchers and practitioners navigate the fragmented literature, identifying consolidated solutions as well as open research gaps in the field.

B. Research questions

To guide this investigation and achieve the objectives outlined in the introduction, we defined a set of specific research questions (RQs). These questions were systematically structured using the PICOC framework proposed by Petticrew & Roberts [8], a method that ensures all key facets of the research topic are covered. The application of PICOC was as follows:

Population (P): The target domain of the investigation, which is the field of Model-Driven Software Engineering (MDSE). **Intervention (I):** The core phenomenon under study: the mechanisms and techniques for change tracking and evolution management. **Comparison (C):** This element was deemed not applicable, as the goal is to map existing solutions rather than compare interventions. **Outcome (O):** The results of interest we aim to extract from the literature, namely the proposed approaches, tools, and strategies for traceability. **Context (C):** The specific setting where the intervention occurs, which is the management of model evolution and change. This structured definition directly led to the formulation of the following four research questions:

- RQ1** What approaches have been proposed to support change traceability in model-based programming or related model-driven contexts?
- RQ2** What types of changes are addressed by existing traceability solutions?
- RQ3** Which tools or frameworks provide mechanisms for managing and tracing model evolution?

RQ4 What trends and gaps can be identified in the literature concerning methods, technologies, and strategies for traceability in MDSE?

Furthermore, the keywords and synonyms identified for each PICOC element served as the foundational building blocks for systematically constructing the search string.

C. Search Process

To perform the search, we selected digital libraries that meet three core requirements: they must (i) provide a web-based search engine; (ii) support queries using Boolean operators; and (iii) contain a comprehensive index of peer-reviewed computer science literature.

The selection includes the following five major databases: (1) ACM Digital Library (2) EI Compendex (3) IEEE Xplore Digital Library (4) Scopus (5) Springer-Link. We queried these databases using a general search string, which is detailed below. To define the search string, we used the terms and synonyms identified during the PICOC analysis. The boolean operator “OR” was used to combine alternative terms and synonyms within each PICOC element, and the boolean operator “AND” was used to link the main concepts of Population, Intervention, Outcome, and Context. The resulting string—with the PICOC elements—is presented in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: Search string

D. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

A key activity during the SMS planning is the definition of the inclusion criteria (IC) and exclusion criteria (EC). These criteria are fundamental to the selection process, providing a systematic basis for filtering the studies returned by the search engines. For a paper to be selected, it must satisfy at least one inclusion criterion. Conversely, if a paper meets any single exclusion criterion, it is removed from consideration. For the SMS, we defined the following IC and EC:

Inclusion Criteria (IC): IC1 The study proposes or describes an approach, technique, or method for tracking

changes and evolution in models within the context of MDE. **IC2** The study addresses the use of change tracking mechanisms to support one or more activities in the modeling process. **IC3** The primary study proposes or describes a tool, framework, or plug-in that supports change tracking in models.

Exclusion Criteria (EC): **EC1** The study's main scope is irrelevant to the MDSE domain. **EC2** The study does not address model change tracking in any way. **EC3** The study discusses a different form of change tracking, such as requirements traceability, or focuses on alternative types of models like mathematical or physical models. **EC4** The study was not peer-reviewed. **EC5** The primary study is written in a language other than English.

E. Quality assessment

The purpose of the quality assessment (QA) is to evaluate the selected studies as a means of measuring their rigor and relevance to the research questions. Each of the following four quality assessment criteria (QAC) was evaluated for every primary study, in accordance with the following grade: Y (Yes) = 1 point; P (Partially) = 0.5 points; and N (No) = 0 points. The final score for each study was calculated as the weighted sum of the four criteria, with a maximum possible score of 10.0. This score was not used to exclude studies, but rather to contextualize their contributions during the analysis. The QAC and their evaluation guidelines are as follows:

QAC1 Does the study contextualize MDE and demonstrate the need for change tracking in this area? (**W=1,5**)

Y: The study clearly contextualizes MDSE and justifies the need for change tracking.

P: The study provides a partial contextualization.

N: The study does not contextualize MDSE.

QAC2 Does the study propose, use, or describe any approach or mechanism for change tracking in detail? (**W=3,5**)

Y: The approach or mechanism is clearly proposed and described in detail.

P: The mechanism is mentioned or described briefly.

N: No specific mechanism is proposed or described.

QAC3 Does the study propose, use, or describe a tool, framework, or environment for change tracking in MDE? (**W=3**)

Y: The study clearly describes or proposes a functional tool, framework, or environment.

P: An artifact is mentioned, but without technical details or evidence of effective use.

N: No tool, or framework, is mentioned.

QAC4 Does the study provide relevant contributions to the field of change tracking in MDE? (**W=2**)

Y: The study provides a relevant and recognizable contribution that advances the field.

P: The contribution is marginal or not innovative.

N: No identifiable contribution is made.

Finally, based on the weighted sum of these criteria, the studies were categorized according to the following quality scale to support the analysis: *Rejected* (score < 6.0), *Fair* (6.0 ≤ score < 7.0), *Good* (7.0 ≤ score < 8.0), *Very Good* (8.0 ≤ score < 9.0), and *Excellent* (score ≥ 9.0).

F. Selection process

The selection process was divided into five main steps, following a funnel-like approach to progressively filter the studies. This process was performed by the author to ensure a systematic selection. The steps are described as follows:

Step 1 – Database Search: The process began by executing the search string across the selected digital libraries. In this initial step, we applied filters directly in the search engines, where available, to exclude articles based on EC4 (non-peer-reviewed) and EC5 (language).

Step 2 – Duplicate Removal: The records retrieved from all databases were exported and subsequently uploaded to the Parsifal² platform. This tool was used to automatically identify and remove duplicate entries, creating a unified dataset of unique studies.

Step 3 – Intermediate Screening: In this step, a preliminary review of the titles and abstracts of each study was conducted. In cases where the title and abstract were not sufficient for a clear decision, the introduction and conclusion sections were also read. The goal of this phase was to filter out clearly irrelevant papers by applying inclusion criteria IC1, IC2, IC3 and exclusion criteria EC1, EC2, EC3, ensuring that only relevant studies proceeded to the next stage of review.

Step 4 – Full-Text Review: All studies that remained after the intermediate screening were retrieved for a complete full-text reading. The same inclusion and exclusion criteria from the previous step were applied again, but this time to the entire content of the article to make the final selection decision by the author of this work.

Step 5 – Quality Assessment: Finally, the studies included in the final set were evaluated based on the quality assessment criteria defined in the previous subsection. This step was not intended to exclude further studies, but to provide a qualitative measure of their rigor and relevance for the analysis of the results.

G. Data extraction strategy

To extract the relevant data from the selected papers, we designed a systematic extraction form. This form was structured to answer the research questions and to characterize the technical landscape of change tracking in MDSE. The extracted data allows us to classify the studies regarding their research maturity, the technical approach adopted for change detection, the tool support provided, and the methods used for validation. The following data were extracted for each primary study during the execution of the research:

²<https://parsif.al/>

- **General Characteristics:**

- *Research Type*: Classification of the research method (e.g., Solution Proposal, Evaluation Research, Survey, Experience Report, etc.);
- *Contribution Type*: The main artifact produced (e.g., Method/Technique, Tool/Framework, Model/Metamodel, Empirical Evidence);
- *Validation Method*: How the authors demonstrated the validity of the proposal (e.g., Proof of Concept, Empirical Study, Industrial Case Study, Performance Benchmark, or Theoretical Analysis).

- **Change Tracking Approach:**

- *Paradigm*: The fundamental philosophy for perceiving changes (State/Operation-based, Hybrid);
- *Detection Strategy*: The specific algorithm used (e.g., Post-hoc Differencing, ID-based Matching, Signature-based, Operation Recording);
- *Representation*: How changes are structured (e.g., Delta Model, Edit Script/Log, Annotated Model, Visual Diff, or Matrix);
- *Goal*: The primary motivation for the tracking mechanism (e.g., Versioning/SCM, Model Migration, Conflict Detection/Merge, Understanding/Visualization, etc.).

- **Semantics and Granularity:**

- *Change Granularity*: The abstraction level of the supported changes (e.g., Atomic/Low-level, Composite/Pattern-based, Visual, or Textual);
- *Semantic Awareness*: Whether the approach interprets the meaning of the change (e.g., Syntactic Only, Semantically Rich, User-defined Rules, or Consistency Checking).

- **Tool Support:**

- *Tool*: Name of the tool or prototype (if available);
- *Environment*: The technological environment (e.g., Eclipse/EMF Plugin, Standalone Desktop, Web-based, or VCS Integrated);
- *Target Model*: The type of model supported (e.g., Generic/Metamodel Independent, UML, BPMN, DSLs, or SysML);
- *Visualization Support*: How changes are presented to the user (e.g., Tree View, Graphical Overlay, Side-by-side, or Natural Language);
- *Availability*: Accessibility of the artifact (Open Source, Commercial, or Not Available).

- **Qualitative Data:**

- *Reported Gaps*: Limitations and future works explicitly mentioned (e.g., Scalability, Cognitive Load, Semantic Gap, Interoperability).

The extraction process was performed by the author. Data were recorded using a spreadsheet³ to facilitate the analysis presented in Section IV.

³This spreadsheet includes not only the data extraction but also the Quality Assessment and other aspects of the study; see Section VIII.

III. CONDUCTION

The conduction of this SMS followed the protocol and phases described in Section II. The process was executed to ensure a rigorous identification of primary studies relevant to change tracking in MDSE. The following subsections detail the results obtained from the database search, the application of inclusion and exclusion criteria, and the quality assessment of the selected studies.

A. Database search and criteria-based selection

The search phase was performed by executing the defined search string across the five selected electronic databases. As summarized in Table I, a total of 3818 studies were initially retrieved (Step 1). Following the data extraction, the duplicate removal process (Step 2) identified and excluded 1253 redundant records, resulting in a unique set of 2565 papers to be screened. It is worth noting that Compendex and Scopus provided the highest number of returned papers, accounting for a significant portion of the initial dataset.

TABLE I: Search engines and retrieved primary studies

Database	Step 1	Step 2	Step 3	Step 4	Step 5
ACM DL	52	49	7	5	0
Compendex	1204	616	43	18	13
IEEE Xplore	828	705	34	28	11
SCOPUS	1256	730	42	25	7
SpringerLink	478	465	55	29	6
Total	3818	2565	163	105	37

Subsequently, the selection process involved a multi-stage filtering approach as depicted in Figure 2. In the intermediate screening (Step 3), the titles and abstracts of the 2565 unique papers were analyzed against the inclusion and exclusion criteria, resulting in the selection of 163 potentially relevant studies. These candidates were then subjected to a full-text review (Step 4), where the analysis led to the exclusion of 58 papers that did not fully meet the scope of the research. Finally, during the quality assessment phase (Step 5), the remaining 105 papers were re-evaluated to ensure methodological rigor, resulting in a final set of 37 primary studies.

B. Study QA

To assess the trustworthiness and relevance of the selected primary studies, the Quality Assessment (QA) criteria defined in Section II were applied to the 37 papers included in the final set. Table II presents the detailed scores for each study across the four criteria, along with their final calculated score and qualitative description. The evaluation demonstrates that the selected studies possess a high degree of quality, with the majority classified as "Good", "Very Good", or "Excellent".

TABLE II: Quality Studies Scores

Studies		QAC		Quality		Studies		QAC		Quality							
ID	Reference	Year	1	2	3	4	Sc	Des	ID	Reference	Year	1	2	3	4	Sc	Des
01	[9] Porres	2003	Y	Y	Y	P	9	E	20	[10] Kehrer	2012	Y	Y	Y	Y	10	E
02	[11] Ivkovic	2004	Y	Y	P	Y	8,5	V	21	[12] Mendez	2012	Y	Y	Y	P	9	E
03	[13] Porres	2005	Y	Y	P	P	7,5	G	22	[14] Fadhel	2012	Y	Y	P	P	7,5	G
04	[15] Grunske	2005	Y	P	Y	P	7,25	G	23	[16] Kehrer	2013	Y	Y	P	P	7,5	G
05	[17] Grunske	2005	P	Y	P	P	6,75	F	24	[18] Agirre	2014	Y	P	P	Y	6,75	F
06	[19] Buttner	2006	Y	Y	P	N	6,5	F	25	[20] Koshima	2014	P	P	Y	P	6,5	F
07	[21] Reiter	2007	Y	Y	P	P	7,5	G	26	[22] Maier	2015	P	Y	P	P	6,75	F
08	[23] Robbes	2008	Y	Y	Y	Y	10	E	27	[24] Mehmood	2016	Y	Y	Y	Y	10	E
09	[25] Koegel	2008	Y	Y	Y	P	9	E	28	[26] Zhang	2017	Y	Y	P	P	7,5	G
10	[27] Rath	2008	P	Y	P	Y	7,75	G	29	[28] Rossini	2018	Y	Y	P	P	7,5	G
11	[29] Correa	2008	Y	Y	P	P	7,5	G	30	[30] Maoz	2018	Y	Y	N	P	6	F
12	[6] Altmanninger	2009	Y	Y	Y	Y	10	E	31	[31] Somogyi	2018	Y	Y	N	P	6	F
13	[32] Gerth	2009	Y	Y	P	Y	8,5	V	32	[33] Zadahmad	2019	Y	P	Y	P	7,25	G
14	[34] Kolovos	2009	Y	P	Y	P	7,25	G	33	[35] Nieke	2021	Y	Y	P	Y	8,5	V
15	[36] Koegel	2010	Y	Y	Y	Y	10	E	34	[37] Zadahmad	2022	Y	P	P	Y	6,75	F
16	[38] Konemann	2010	Y	Y	P	P	7,5	G	35	[39] Jafarlou	2023	Y	Y	Y	Y	10	E
17	[40] Almanninger	2010	Y	P	Y	P	7,25	G	36	[41] Pietron	2023	Y	Y	N	Y	7	G
18	[42] Maoz	2011	Y	Y	P	Y	8,5	V	37	[43] Homolka	2024	Y	Y	Y	Y	10	E
19	[44] Taentzer	2012	Y	Y	Y	Y	10	E									

Legend - Y: Yes, N: No, P: Partly, Sc: Score, Des: Description, F: Fair, G: Good, V: Very Good, E: Excellent.

Fig. 2: Study selection process

Reviewing the scores reveals that the selected primary studies provide a solid foundation for this SMS. This high overall quality ensures the reliability of the data extracted and discussed in the following sections.

IV. DISCUSSION: ANSWERING THE RQS

In this section, we present the main findings obtained from the analysis of the selected primary studies. The discussion is structured according to the research questions defined in the planning phase.

RQ1 What approaches have been proposed to support change traceability in model-based programming or related model-driven contexts?

The analysis of the selected studies reveals that change tracking approaches in MDSE are fundamentally categorized into two main paradigms, distinguished by the timing and method of change detection: State-based and Operation-based. As established in foundational surveys and taxonomies [6], [36], [41], this distinction defines the core strategy for perceiving model evolution. The State-based approach, which constitutes the predominant paradigm in the analyzed corpus [11], [21], [24], [29], [32], operates in a post-hoc manner. It detects changes by comparing two distinct versions (snapshots) of a model, typically a base version and a modified version, using algorithms to calculate the difference only after the editing session is complete [10], [33], [44]. Conversely, the Operation-based paradigm [9], [13], [25] focuses on capturing evolution in real-time. Instead of comparing final states, this approach records editing events or commands as they occur within the modeling environment, effectively creating a sequential log of the user's actions [20], [23], [43]. While State-based solutions are frequently adopted for their ability to function independently of the editing tool [22], Operation-based methods are highlighted for preserving the temporal order and the specific intent of the changes, although they often require tighter integration with the IDE infrastructure [30], [35].

It is worth noting that the distinction between these paradigms is not always mutually exclusive. Recognizing the trade-offs between the interoperability of state-based approaches and the precise intent capture

of operation-based ones, some studies adopt a hybrid strategy or investigate the interplay between both methods. For instance, [15] combines graph transformation rules with state consistency checks to support model synchronization, while [36] explores the integration of both paradigms to improve change understanding. The quantitative distribution of the primary studies across these categories is visually summarized in Figure 3.

Fig. 3: Distribution of change tracking paradigms

Regarding the underlying detection mechanisms, the two paradigms face distinct challenges. In State-based approaches, the core problem is establishing a precise correspondence (matching) between elements of disconnected versions. To address this, a significant portion of studies employs ID-based matching [11], [24], [29], relying on persistent unique identifiers (UUIDs) to link elements deterministically. While efficient, this strategy is brittle if the modeling tool does not preserve IDs during export/import cycles. Consequently, alternative approaches utilize Heuristic or Similarity-based matching [14], [34], which infer correspondence by analyzing element signatures, names, or structural neighbors. Although more flexible, heuristics entail a higher computational cost and the risk of false positives. Notably, mature solutions often implement a hybrid strategy, prioritizing IDs and falling back on heuristics for unmatched elements to balance precision and flexibility [44].

In contrast, Operation-based strategies [9], [23], [43] circumvent the complex matching phase entirely. By integrating directly into the editing environment, these approaches utilize Command Stacks or event listeners to intercept and record changes (e.g., create, update, move) as they happen. As emphasized in [20], this strategy offers the distinct advantage of capturing the user’s exact semantic intent and the temporal order of events, preventing the loss of information common in post-hoc comparisons. However, this comes at the cost of interoperability: while state-based methods operate on standard serialized files (agnostic to the editor), operation-based methods typically require a specific, often closed, tool environment to capture the execution trace [25], [30].

Figure 4 presents the distribution of the specific technical strategies employed to detect changes. The results

highlight a polarization between the two primary mechanisms. On one hand, *Operation Recording* stands out as the most frequent strategy (12 studies), corroborating the trend towards capturing the user’s intent in real-time. On the other hand, *ID-based* matching remains a robust competitor (11 studies), serving as the *de facto* standard for state-based approaches where persistent identifiers are available. Furthermore, the presence of *Heuristic* matching (8 studies) underscores the ongoing challenge of comparing models when IDs are unreliable or absent, necessitating similarity-based algorithms.

Fig. 4: Prevalence of change detection strategies

Beyond the detection mechanism, a critical aspect identified in the literature is how the detected changes are computationally represented and persisted. Once identified, changes must be structured into an artifact that can be processed by other tools. The analysis highlights two primary forms of representation. The first and most common are Difference Models (or Delta Models) [24], which structure the changes as a model in itself, often a graph containing the added, deleted, or modified elements. This approach treats the “delta” as a first-class citizen, allowing the difference to be manipulated, validated, or transformed just like any other model. The second common form consists of Edit Scripts [16], which represent changes as a linear sequence of imperative instructions (e.g., a log of atomic operations) that, when executed, transform the original model into the new version. While Edit Scripts are the natural output of operation-based approaches, they can also be generated post-hoc. A notable trend observed in recent studies is the effort to decouple these representations from specific tools, creating platform-independent formats that facilitate complex activities such as model patching, migration, and co-evolution.

RQ2 What types of changes are addressed by existing traceability solutions?

Regarding the granularity of changes, the literature reveals a clear stratification. At the foundational level, virtually all analyzed approaches support the detection of Atomic or low-level changes, such as the creation/deletion of model elements or attribute updates [11], [24], [29]. While this granularity is sufficient for data serialization, it often results in verbose difference models that fail to convey the modeler’s intent, leading to high cognitive load. To bridge this gap, a significant trend has emerged towards Composite change detection. Recent studies emphasize the need for ‘Semantic Lifting’—a process of inferring high-level editing operations (e.g., refactorings) from sets of atomic deltas. Notable examples include the SiLift framework [10], [16], which employs graph transformation rules to recognize complex edit patterns, and the hierarchical detection algorithms proposed by Zhang et al. [26]. Furthermore, approaches like DSMCompare [33], [37], [39] extend this concept to Domain-Specific Languages (DSLs), demonstrating that moving from graph-level differences to domain-specific composite operations is essential for improving human comprehension of model evolution.

Figure 5 illustrates this landscape. As observed, while approximately 30% of the studies remain restricted to Atomic Only changes, the majority addresses the semantic gap by supporting composite operations. Specifically, 48.7% of the works adopt a hybrid approach (Atomic & Composite), building high-level understanding on top of low-level traces, while 21.6% are Composite Focused, dedicating their contributions exclusively to the algorithms of refactoring detection and pattern matching.

Fig. 5: Distribution of change granularity support

Closely related to granularity is the concept of Semantic Awareness, a term used with varying interpretations across the surveyed literature. In many studies, particularly earlier ones like [9] and [11], the claim of being “semantically rich” primarily refers to Consistency Checking. In this context, the tracking mechanism

ensures that changes result in a “well-formed” model that adheres to metamodel constraints (e.g., cardinalities, type conformance), rather than interpreting the intent of the change itself. A more rigorous theoretical distinction is provided by the “Manifesto for Semantic Model Differencing” [42], which explicitly separates Syntactic Differencing from Semantic Differencing. While syntactic differencing detects modifications in the underlying graph structure (e.g., adding an orphan class), semantic differencing determines whether the actual behavior or meaning of the model has changed (e.g., determining if that orphan class impacts the system’s execution). To address this challenge practically, especially within Domain-Specific Languages (DSLs), recent approaches have shifted towards User-defined Rules [37]. This strategy allows language engineers to define specific patterns that constitute meaningful changes in their domain, effectively customizing the notion of semantics beyond generic structural comparison. This distribution of semantic awareness is depicted in Figure 6. While early or generic approaches focused on Syntactic Only comparison (18.9%) or basic Consistency Checking (8.1%), the majority of the analyzed literature (62.2%) now claims to be Semantically Rich, incorporating some form of intent detection or behavioral analysis. Notably, User-defined Rules have emerged as a distinct category (10.8%), validating the trend towards customizable semantics for Domain-Specific Languages

Fig. 6: Distribution of semantic awareness levels

RQ3 Which tools or frameworks provide mechanisms for managing and tracing model evolution?

The analysis of the selected studies allowed for the identification of 17 distinct named tools or frameworks specifically designed to support model evolution tracking. The technological landscape revealed by these artifacts is highly heterogeneous, ranging from robust, industrially-applied open-source frameworks to academic prototypes developed solely for the purpose of conceptual validation. Table III presents an overview of the named tools identified in this review, detailing their target models and technical environments.

TABLE III: Tools overview

Tool Name	Target Model	Environment	Reference
AMOR	Generic (Metamodel Indep.)	Eclipse / EMF Plugin	[44]
Change Factory	Smalltalk (AST)	IDE Agnostic	[23]
DiCoMEF	Generic (Metamodel Indep.)	Eclipse / EMF Plugin	[20]
DSMCompare	DSLs (Sirius/Graphical)	Eclipse / EMF Plugin	[33], [37], [39]
EMF Compare	Generic (Metamodel Indep.)	Eclipse / EMF Plugin	[12], [34], [36]
Fujaba	UML	Standalone Desktop	[15], [17]
HLLA	UML	Eclipse / EMF Plugin	[26]
Odyssey-MEC	UML	Web-based	[29]
SiLift	Generic / UML	Eclipse / EMF Plugin	[10], [16]
SMoVer	Generic (Metamodel Indep.)	Eclipse / EMF Plugin	[40]
SMW	Generic / UML	IDE Agnostic / Python Script	[9], [13]
Sisyphus (TIME)	Generic (Metamodel Indep.)	Standalone Desktop	[25]
TemporalReg3000	Generic (Metamodel Indep.)	Eclipse / EMF Plugin	[35]
TransEvol	Generic / UML	Eclipse / EMF Plugin	[18]
UNICASE	Generic (Metamodel Indep.)	Eclipse / EMF Plugin	[36]
USE	UML (Class Diagrams + OCL)	Standalone Desktop	[19]
VIATRA2	DSLs / Generic	Eclipse / EMF Plugin	[27]

Consistently reflecting the trends in MDSE, the technical landscape is heavily dominated by the Eclipse Modeling Framework (EMF). As illustrated in Figure 7, the majority of the analyzed solutions are implemented as Eclipse plug-ins. This hegemony can be attributed to the de facto standardization provided by the Ecore metamodel and the XMI serialization format, which significantly facilitates interoperability between different modeling tools. Consequently, prominent frameworks such as SiLift [10], AMOR [44], and DSMCompare [33] are built not as standalone applications, but as extensions within this ecosystem, leveraging its underlying infrastructure for model management and editor integration.

Fig. 7: Distribution of technical environments

Regarding the scope of applicability, the tools can be categorized based on their target models, as illustrated in Figure 8. A substantial number of frameworks, such as EMF Compare [34] and SiLift [10], fall into the “Metamodel Independent” category. These tools oper-

ate directly on the underlying meta-modeling standard (e.g., Ecore or MOF), allowing them to track changes in any model instance. Conversely, earlier solutions like Odyssey-MEC [29] were frequently tailored specifically for UML, while recent trends favor Domain-Specific Languages (DSLs), exemplified by DSMCompare [37]. The intersection in the diagram highlights approaches that, while technically generic, require domain-specific configurations or were explicitly adapted for specific languages in the reported studies.

Fig. 8: Distribution of target models support

In summary, the answer to RQ3 reveals a heterogeneous landscape composed of 17 distinct tools, ranging from academic prototypes to robust frameworks. The evidence confirms that the technical environment is heavily centered on the Eclipse ecosystem, driven by the standardization of EMF. Regarding the scope, the available solutions are distributed between generic, metamodel-independent approaches and those tailored for specific domains, with a notable intersection where generic tools are adapted to handle specific languages.

RQ4 What trends and gaps can be identified in the literature concerning methods, technologies, and strategies for traceability in MDSE?

A longitudinal analysis of the primary studies reveals a distinct evolution in the focus of research, shifting from infrastructure to semantic understanding. In the early years of the analyzed period (2003–2010), efforts were largely concentrated on solving the fundamental algorithmic challenges of model synchronization and low-level change detection, often targeting generic meta-models or UML [9], [11]. However, a significant trend observed from 2012 onwards is the move towards “Semantic Lifting” and high-level change detection. Recent research has increasingly focused on bridging the gap between graph-level differences and domain-specific concepts, moving away from “one-size-fits-all” solutions. This is evident in the rise of approaches tailored for Domain-Specific Languages (DSLs) and the incorporation of user-defined rules to capture the specific intent of the modeler, as seen in frameworks like DSMCompare [37], [39]. This trajectory suggests that the community is largely changing focus from the problem of how to calculate differences and is now focused on what those differences mean in specific domains.

A recurring gap reported in the literature [15], [35], [44] is the performance degradation of matching algorithms when applied to large-scale industrial models. Heuristic and similarity-based matching techniques, while flexible, often suffer from high computational complexity (e.g., subgraph isomorphism problems), leading to exponential execution times or prohibitive memory consumption. While many approaches perform well on “toy examples” or small datasets, the evidence suggests that efficient, real-time change tracking for massive models with lots of elements remains an open challenge, often requiring trade-offs between the precision of the match and the speed of execution.

Finally, the literature highlights a fundamental trade-off between Semantic Precision and Interoperability, often referred to as the “Semantic Gap”. State-based approaches, which dominate the landscape due to their compatibility with any editing tool, struggle to reconstruct the exact user intent (e.g., distinguishing a “Refactoring” from a “Delete/Create” sequence) [16], [20]. Conversely, Operation-based approaches capture the intent perfectly but require a closed, specific editing environment, hindering tool chain interoperability. Bridging this gap remains an active and necessary area for future research to support sophisticated evolution scenarios like model merging and co-evolution.

V. THREATS TO VALIDITY

This section discusses the potential threats to the validity of the study and the procedures adopted to mitigate them, based on the principles established by Wohlin *et al.* [45] and Verdaccia *et al.* [46].

Construct Validity: This aspect concerns whether the study actually measures what it claims to measure. A primary risk is the potential omission of relevant

primary studies due to limitations in the search string or the selected databases. To mitigate this threat, a rigorous search protocol was defined and executed. The search string was systematically constructed using the PICOC framework, including relevant synonyms, and was applied to five major scientific databases (ACM, IEEE, Scopus, Springer, and Compendex), ensuring a comprehensive coverage of the literature.

Internal Validity: This relates to the rigor of the study execution and the influence of extraneous variables. A significant threat in this work is the potential for personal bias during the selection and classification processes, as the entire SMS, including screening, full-text reading, and quality assessment, was conducted by a single researcher. As this study was developed within the scope of an individual academic course assignment, cross-validation by a second reviewer or consensus meetings were not feasible. Therefore, subjective decisions during the filtering phases represent an acknowledged and unmitigated threat.

Conclusion Validity: This concerns the ability to draw correct conclusions from the gathered data. There is a risk that the extracted information was misinterpreted or categorized incorrectly, potentially leading to inaccurate answers to the research questions. Similar to the internal validity threat, the absence of independent data extraction or peer review means that the analysis relies solely on the interpretation of the author. While data extraction forms were used to standardize the process, the risk of interpretive bias remains present.

VI. RELATED WORK

In the last decade, several secondary studies have addressed different aspects of model management, evolution, and maintenance within the context of Model-Driven Engineering (MDE). These works provide a baseline for understanding how software artifacts are compared, versioned, and traced.

Stephan and Cordy [47] conducted a survey focused specifically on model comparison approaches. They classified existing techniques based on the types of models they support—ranging from UML and Simulink to generic metamodels—and analyzed how model matching is accomplished, highlighting the prevalence of similarity-based strategies at that time. Although their work establishes the fundamental algorithmic landscape for model differencing, it is strictly limited to the state-based paradigm due to the nature of model matching.

Similarly, Gonçalves *et al.* [48] performed a systematic mapping study aimed at classifying techniques for design model comparison. By analyzing 40 primary studies, they categorized the literature based on diagram types (e.g., UML vs. Generic) and research methods, concluding that the field was largely composed of solution proposals with limited empirical validation. While their work offers a valuable statistical view of the area up to

2014, it focuses primarily on the structural comparison of visual diagrams. Our study complements this view by addressing the broader problem of change tracking and capturing the evolution of the field over the last decade.

Santiago et al. [49] presented a systematic literature review on traceability management in MDSE, analyzing how relationships between different software artifacts are created, stored, and maintained. Their study provides deep insights into the automation of trace links and the CRUD operations supported by existing tools. However, their definition of traceability is primarily focused on inter-artifact links (e.g., linking requirements to models) across the development lifecycle. In contrast, our mapping focuses on the traceability of model evolution itself—specifically, how changes within a model are tracked, represented, and understood over time (versioning), rather than linking distinct artifacts.

Therefore, while these secondary studies provide the foundational background for model comparison and traceability, this systematic mapping differs by providing an updated and more specific perspective on change tracking. Furthermore, our study covers the technological landscape of the last decade, mapping the currently available tools and addressing specific gaps.

VII. FINAL REMARKS AND FUTURE WORKS

This paper presented a systematic mapping study aimed at characterizing the state-of-the-art of change tracking in Model-Driven Software Engineering. Through a selection process applied to an initial set of 2565 records, 37 primary studies were selected and analyzed. The results provided a comprehensive overview of the field, classifying the existing approaches into state-based and operation-based paradigms, mapping the technical landscape of 17 distinct tools, and identifying the evolution of research trends regarding change granularity and semantic awareness over the last two decades.

The evidence suggests that while change tracking in MDSE is an active and maturing research area, it is far from being a solved problem. The community has successfully addressed fundamental challenges regarding low-level difference calculation, shifting the focus towards complex problems such as semantic understanding and domain-specific adaptation. However, significant gaps remain. Issues related to scalability, the cognitive load of visualization, and the trade-off between tool interoperability and precision indicate that there is still ample room for innovation.

As future work, we intend to expand and refine this mapping study. This involves replicating specific stages of the selection and data extraction process with multiple reviewers and a more extensive timeframe to mitigate the validity threats identified in this work. Furthermore, we aim to leverage the technical findings and architectural patterns identified in this study to guide the

development of a new environment for model-based programming. This tool will be designed to address the reported gaps, implementing a change tracking mechanism that balances semantic richness with usability.

VIII. DATA AVAILABILITY

We are committed to promoting transparency and reproducibility in research. In line with this commitment, we provide all the data supporting the findings of the study, which is openly available on Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17782418>.

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